

Stiffness decoding methods for prosthetics: a comparison in simulation

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I. INTRODUCTION

Movement originates from the central nervous system, which changes the mechanical impedance of the neuromuscular system by acting as a kind of adaptive parameter control. Hogan [1] proposed that prostheses with adaptable impedance could improve natural motion and environmental interaction. Nevertheless, Variable stiffness increases the complexity of many aspects of a prosthesis, raising the question of whether variable stiffness can benefit the user or whether fixed stiffness would always be preferable. Sensinger *et al.* [4] faced such a question from the viewpoint of prosthetic control, concluding that large impedance values allow faster and more accurate results. However, Blank *et al.* [3] demonstrated the existence of optimal task-dependent stiffness values. More recently, Capsi Morales *et al.* [2] implemented a simultaneous, proportional control method to command both the position and stiffness of the prostheses, with promising results. To investigate the differences in their findings, we compare the previous stiffness decoding techniques in simulation.

II. MUSCLE MODEL AND STIFFNESS DECODING

The muscle group acting on the elbow has been shaped by two opposing muscles: biceps and triceps [1]. The forearm and hand are modeled as a rigid link of inertia I and mass m . The link is driven by two antagonistic actuators subject to gravity and an external torque load. The dynamic equation is as follows:

$$I\ddot{\vartheta} = T(u_b - u_t) - K(u_b + u_t)\vartheta + mgl \sin \vartheta - B\dot{\vartheta} + w \quad (1)$$

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Fig. 1: Model simulation: (a) Neural controls u_b and u_t were simulated as sine waves between 0 and 1. (b) Muscle torques as $\tau_b = (T - K\theta)u_b$ and $\tau_t = -(T + K\theta)u_t$. (c) EMG signals and processing phases.

Where ϑ is the angle the link forms with the vertical, $\dot{\vartheta}$ is the angular velocity of the limb, $\ddot{\vartheta}$ is the angular acceleration of the limb, K is the angular stiffness, T is the maximum isometric torque, w is the external torque, $mgl \sin \theta$ is the gravitational contribution, u_b e u_t are neural controls.

Muscles simultaneously control joint torques, velocities, positions and impedances [5]. The coupling of all those variables, both on the input side of the muscle activation and on the output side of mechanical limb behavior, makes the problem of simultaneous stiffness and position decoding non trivial.

Approaches in literature usually attempt the simultaneous decoding of stiffness by using a measure of muscle co-contraction, which can be extracted as the minimum or average of the EMG signals. We considered three stiffness decoding methods. In the first method (**Vsp**), stiffness decreases as the

minimum-evaluated co-contraction increases [4]:

$$\sigma_{cmd} = \sigma_{cmd}^{min} + K_1 \min(EMG_1, EMG_2) \quad (2)$$

Where σ_{cmd}^{min} is the minimum stiffness value, $\min(EMG_1, EMG_2)$ is the co-contraction of the pair of muscles, K_1 is the stiffness gain so that maximum stiffness is reached with just 30% co-contraction.

In the second method (**Vsm**) stiffness increases as the minimum-evaluated co-contraction increases [4]:

$$\sigma_{cmd} = \sigma_{cmd}^{max} - K_2 \min(EMG_1, EMG_2), \quad (3)$$

Where σ_{cmd}^{max} is the maximum stiffness value, K_2 is the stiffness gain so that minimum stiffness is reached at 30% co-contraction.

In the third method (**Vsw**) stiffness increases as the average-evaluated co-contraction increases [2] :

$$\sigma_{cmd} = \sigma_{cmd}^{min} + K_1 \text{mean}(EMG_1, EMG_2). \quad (4)$$

Where $\text{mean}(EMG_1, EMG_2)$ is the co-contraction of the pair of muscles.

Position decoding is often based on so-called proportional velocity controls (**PVCs**), where the position command is proportional to the integral of the difference of the EMG signals [4]. Another method uses a finite state machine (**FSM**) to detect a class of motion: flexion, extension, and stay [2].

A. Muscle Simulation

Fig. 1 shows the simulated evolution of a human elbow modeled as in (1). The EMG signal is modeled as time-varying white Gaussian noise, with a linear relationship between rectified mean value and isometric torque up to 30% of maximum voluntary contraction [1]. Fig. 1 also shows the effect of rectification and low-pass filtering on the EMG signals, imitating the signal conditioning stage of a typical prosthetic EMG input device.

B. Prosthesis Model

To compare the different decoding methods (PVC-Vsm, PVC-Vsp, FSM-Vsw) we applied them to a prosthesis modeled as a mass-spring-damping system. It follows the below dynamic:

$$m\ddot{x} = -b(\dot{x} - \dot{x}_{cmd}) - \sigma_{cmd}(x - x_{cmd}) + F_{env} \quad (5)$$

Where m is the mass of the system, b is the damping, F_{env} is the external force acting on the prosthesis, x_{cmd} and σ_{cmd} are the commanded signals, x, \dot{x}, \ddot{x} are the position, velocity and acceleration of the virtual prosthesis.

III. RESULTS

A comparison between the nominal elbow stiffness and the ones derived from the application of models (2), (3), and (4) is shown in Fig. 2. The minimum method reflects pure co-contraction and is more sensitive to low activation level. The average method provides a more balanced stiffness, which takes into account the activation of both muscles.

Fig. 2: Comparison of stiffness decoding strategies: the average-based method demonstrates behavior more closely aligned to nominal elbow stiffness than the minimum-based method.

IV. DISCUSSION

This study investigates the potential of Variable Stiffness control techniques in prosthetics and researches a realistic stiffness decoding technique. The simulation results suggest greater realism for the average-based method. In reaching a reference this decoding technique performs well: despite being a low-stiffness method, it approaches the performance of high-stiffness method. It represents a good trade-off when also considering the implementation of the interaction task where we expect low-stiffness methods to perform better. The decoding method respects the criterion of adaptability, a fundamental requirement especially in dynamic and complex environments. This suggests the validity of the decoding stiffness method based on the average of EMG signals.

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